

Character Development of University Students through the P2KK Program: A Phenomenological Study at the University of Muhammadiyah Malang

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to describe the experiences and perceived meanings of character development among students through the Personality and Leadership Development Program (P2KK) at the University of Muhammadiyah Malang. The research adopts a qualitative approach with Moustakas' phenomenological method. Data were collected through participatory observation, in-depth interviews with student alumni who had participated in the P2KK program, as well as documentation of program activities and the official training modules. The findings indicate that students experienced significant personal transformation throughout the program. They perceived P2KK not as a mere ceremonial activity, but as a space for self-actualization, religious value formation, discipline, social empathy, and leadership development. The meanings derived from these experiences include enhanced spiritual awareness, improved interpersonal skills, and strengthened motivation to achieve as individuals with Islamic character. P2KK is thus experienced as the initial phase of identity formation; preparing students to become not only intellectually capable, but also emotionally and spiritually mature. This study is grounded in Al-Ghazali's theory of moral development, Lickona's character education framework, and Kolb's experiential learning theory. Together, these three theories form a comprehensive and sustainable character education system. The practical implication is that programs like P2KK should continue to be developed and maintained to ensure that graduates are not only intellectually competent, but also ethically and spiritually mature.

KEYWORDS:

Character, student, Phenomenology, P2KK, Experiential Learning, Al-Ghazali

I. INTRODUCTION

New university students represent the younger generation entrusted with the hopes of the nation (In'am, 2023; Soleh et al., 2024). The progress of an era is largely dependent on the youth (Arifin et al., 2024; Amri, 2023). Societal transformation is not the responsibility of those already established in their careers and age, but of the younger generation, university students who are still in the process of pursuing knowledge (Napsiyah et al., 2023). These students, as adolescents transitioning into adulthood, often face challenges related to personal maturation for which they are unprepared (Maulina & Sari, 2018). Issues such as psychological readiness, the development of a personality

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grounded in religious values, and unrefined leadership potential further complicate this transition (Daulay, 2021). Moreover, this generation often labeled as the "strawberry generation" while intellectually resourceful, is also perceived as mentally fragile (Aulia et al., 2022). On the other hand, they are also recognized for their rapid learning capabilities and adaptability to change (Fadli, 2023).

As members of the younger generation and agents of national progress, students are expected to possess the capacity to meet such challenges (Nurpratiwi, 2021). As agents of change, they are required to think critically, act courageously, uphold democratic values, and participate in activities that drive positive transformation (Pertiwi et al., 2021). As intellectuals and valuable members of society, students must be able to position themselves professionally and proportionally within both academic and broader social environments (Utami & Najicha, 2022). They must also be mentally resilient, embody religiously grounded personal character, and possess well-developed leadership qualities (Firdaus, 2017).

Nurul Hidayah et al, Character Development of University Students through the P2KK Program: A Phenomenological Study at the University of Muhammadiyah Malang

Student character encompasses their daily personality in interaction with their educational setting, family, and community. Soft skills—non-academic, subjective competencies—include moral conduct, internalization of values, appreciation of the arts, motivation, adaptability, communication, teamwork, problem-solving, stress management, and intrinsic leadership abilities that enable individuals to actualize their potential (Adiwaty et al., 2015).

In reality, observations reveal that many first-year university students remain unready to assume their roles as mature individuals tasked with the responsibility of serving as agents of change (Islam et al., 2023). This lack of readiness may result in a psychological burden (Maulina & Sari, 2018) and, in some cases, lead to early academic stress (Adiwaty et al., 2015).

To navigate this transitional period, new students must continuously adjust to themselves, others, and their surroundings. This adjustment involves a reciprocal and dynamic interaction among the self, others, and the environment, each influencing the other (Calhoun & Acocella; Joan Ross, 1995). Adjustment can also be defined as changes within the self and external conditions that are necessary to achieve satisfying relationships and adapt effectively to one's environment (Atwater, 1983; Jeremi & Biromo, 2023)

Recognizing this phenomenon, the University of Muhammadiyah Malang (UMM) initiated a mandatory training program in the 2004/2005 academic year called the Personality and Leadership Development Program (P2KK) (Achmat, 2006). The P2KK is a university-wide program for all new students, designed to foster personal character and leadership skills. This program was created in response to the need for cultivating the personal qualities of students and graduates through a one-week residential system (Haris et al., 2019).

The P2KK program emphasizes character and leadership development—critical aspects of soft skills. It consists of diverse activities and training sessions intended to improve interpersonal communication, leadership ability, and other competencies vital for both academic and professional success (Sunardi et al., 2022).

Each P2KK class is named after an influential Muslim scholar, such as Al-Fārābī, Al-Ghazālī, Al-Khawārizmī, Ibn Khaldūn, Ibn Rushd, Ibn Sīnā, Muhammad ‘Abduh, Rashīd Riḍā, Ar Riḍā, and Muhammad Iqbāl. This naming convention is intended to inspire students to internalize the values and virtues embodied by these figures.

According to the Islamic and Worship Materials Handbook (Haris et al., 2019), P2KK applies an experiential learning approach, offering structured experiences through lectures, simulations, discussions, role-playing, self-assessments, case studies, and outbound activities.

The program's objectives include:

1. providing foundational knowledge of Islamic practices and worship;
2. aligning students' mindsets, attitudes, and behaviors with the university's values (transitioning from "school children" to "university students");
3. equipping new students with academic skills, leadership competencies, and character development grounded in Islamic and Muhammadiyah principles; and
4. developing soft skills relevant to professional environments.

The idea of being “confined” for an entire week without electronic devices (phones, radios, laptops), unable to leave the dormitory, and required to adhere to a strict schedule—such as sleeping at 10:00 PM and waking at 3:00 AM for night prayers, followed by dawn prayer and Quranic reflection until 6:00 AM—can naturally provoke fear, anxiety, and apprehension, even for those with prior boarding school experience.

However, brief observations by the researcher revealed that these feelings of anxiety and discomfort began to dissipate by the second day. By the third day, students showed no signs of anxiety and instead immersed themselves in the shared experiences. Their laughter became genuine, and their positive energy was clearly visible—especially following the outbound sessions.

Strong bonds began to form among the participants, reinforced through structured group tasks designed to support adult learning. These activities required teamwork, collaborative problem-solving, and communal engagement.

This experience aligns with the well-known concept of culture shock, which typically occurs in three stages: fascination, anxiety, and acceptance. Initially, individuals feel excited and fascinated by a new environment; this is followed by anxiety and discomfort due to adaptation challenges; eventually, individuals reach a phase of acceptance and comfort within the new context (Sitorus et al., 2023).

Upon completion of the program, many alumni remain connected through class groups and continue to maintain their relationships through various activities such as reunions and communal events. It is in these interactions that the lasting impact of P2KK becomes evident.

Through its comprehensive content—ranging from Islamic values, worship, and women's jurisprudence (*fiqh an-nisa'*), leadership, personality development, academic culture, and scientific writing—the P2KK program is intended to foster positive character formation among new students, equipping them to navigate both academic life and a mature, with independence and responsibility.

Ideally, graduates are expected to demonstrate a well-grounded practice of worship, a flexible understanding of religion, high self-confidence, and a strong personality. Nevertheless, in practice, some students do not display the anticipated outcomes of the P2KK program, whether in terms

Nurul Hidayah et al, Character Development of University Students through the P2KK Program: A Phenomenological Study at the University of Muhammadiyah Malang

of religiosity or personal character. To explore students' experiences in the P2KK and the meanings they assign to the program, this study was conducted at the Center for Human Resource Education and Training (Pusdiklat SDM), University of Muhammadiyah Malang, the institution responsible for organizing P2KK.

Character development has emerged as a central issue in higher education, particularly within Islamic-based institutions. University of Muhammadiyah Malang (UMM) addresses this need through the P2KK program, which not only introduces students to academic life but also instills Islamic and humanistic values from the outset.

From a classical perspective, Al-Ghazālī emphasized that the goal of education is to purify the soul and cultivate noble character. He believed that character is not innate but can be developed through discipline, habituation, and exemplary role models (Ghazali, 2014; Qasimi (Al), 1995). Al-Ghazālī introduced the concepts of *riyāḍah al-naḥs* (spiritual discipline) and *tazkiyah al-naḥs* (soul purification) as the essence of education (Ghazali (Al), 2008).

In modern thought, Thomas Lickona developed a character education model encompassing three core components: moral knowing, moral feeling, and moral action (Lickona, 2018). These aspects serve as a framework for holistic value internalization (Lickona, 2012), aligning with the integrated character-building approach adopted by P2KK.

Meanwhile, David Kolb's experiential learning theory posits that meaningful learning occurs through a four-stage cycle: concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation (Kolb, 1984). This model is highly relevant to the P2KK implementation, which includes direct activities such as outbound training, group discussions, simulations, and social engagement.

Thus, the theoretical frameworks of Al-Ghazālī, Lickona, and Kolb provide a comprehensive foundation for understanding how P2KK fosters character development through spiritual formation, value internalization, and experiential learning.

Several studies between 2018–2024 emphasize the importance of experiential, value-based, and contextual approaches in shaping students' character. Almaidah, (2018) and Setyowati et al., (2020) confirm P2KK's significant role in soft skill and character development, although phenomenological aspects remain underexplored. Other research highlights the impact of multicultural education, prophetic leadership, religious activities, and anti-corruption values (Nurhakim, (2018); zzet et al., (2020); Nazifah, (2020); Sukino et al., (2021).

Astuti, (2021); Ma'arif, (2022) and Rahman & Dartim, (2023) emphasize the role of Islamic values and leadership styles using phenomenological approaches, while Alvi & Madya, (2023) and Mahdalena et al., (2023) discuss external influences such as family and extracurricular activities. Additional studies underscore character education's potential

to address ethical crises and mental health issues through empathy, tolerance, and integrated learning (Harahap et al., (2024); Nurngain & Imron, (2024); Puspita et al., (2024).

This research gap highlights the lack of comprehensive studies that explore students' transformative experiences in the P2KK program using a phenomenological lens. In essence, the subjective meanings internalized by students throughout and following their participation in the program remain underexplored.

Figure 1. Classification of Previous Research

The present study supports and complements previous findings while enriching them through the use of a phenomenological approach, which enables a holistic exploration of students' subjective meanings. The novelty of this research lies in the application of Moustakas' phenomenological method within the context of the P2KK program—an approach that has rarely been employed in similar studies. Accordingly, the aim of this study is to describe students' experiences in participating in the P2KK program and to understand its significance in shaping their character development.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a qualitative approach using Moustakas' phenomenological method (Moustakas, 1994), which emphasizes understanding the subjective experiences of individuals. This method is particularly suitable for exploring the meaning students derive from their participation in the P2KK program.

Participants were selected purposively, consisting of seven P2KK alumni from various educational backgrounds—some attended Islamic boarding schools, some from public and secular schools, and others from religious-based institutions. Data were collected using: (1) non-participant observation, (2) in-depth semi-structured interviews, and (3) documentation analysis (Sugiyono, (2018); Bungin, (2010)).

Observations were conducted during the P2KK sessions to capture classroom dynamics, participant interactions, and student engagement with Islamic education, worship, and women's jurisprudence (*fiqh an-nisa'*). To explore the participants' experiences and the underlying meaning of the program, in-depth interviews were conducted with P2KK alumni who had completed their studies, guided by open-ended questions and recorded with informed consent.

Nurul Hidayah et al, Character Development of University Students through the P2KK Program: A Phenomenological Study at the University of Muhammadiyah Malang

Documentation included photographs, videos, teaching modules, and program archives to support observational and interview data.

Data analysis followed Moustakas’ five stages of phenomenological analysis (Moustakas, 1994): 1) Epoche: setting aside researcher bias, 2) Horizontalization: identifying significant participant statements, 3) Textural description: describing “what” was experienced, 4) Structural description: exploring “how” it was experienced, and 5) Essence synthesis: integrating both descriptions to convey the essence of the phenomenon. Data validity was ensured using member-checking techniques (Moleong, 2017).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The phenomenological approach aimed to uncover students’ subjective meaning from their P2KK experiences. Hence, findings are presented not only categorically but also through reflective narratives illustrating character transformation from the students’ perspectives.

Observations revealed behavioral changes among participants: greater discipline, cooperation in group activities, and active participation in discussions. Activities such as night prayers, short sermons, and leadership simulations developed spiritual discipline and social awareness.

Initially, students experienced anxiety due to the strict schedule and withdrawal from electronic devices. Over time, they adapted and began to find meaning in the experience. Social interaction, group discussions, religious practices, and experiential learning fostered transformation.

Interviews with participant SP-01N revealed that they initially experienced shock due to the program’s dense and intensive material. However, they acknowledged its benefits in terms of time management and mental resilience. Participant SP-02U, who came from a general (non-religious) school background, described a religious transformation following the P2KK program—even considering wearing a veil (cadar) and feeling more confident in practicing Islamic rituals.

Participant SP-03N expressed enjoyment in the religious classes, although noting that the worship sessions felt somewhat monotonous. Nevertheless, the consistent religious practices served as a motivational trigger to return to a more disciplined, punctual, and steadfast routine, echoing values instilled by their family. Participant SP-04R described a renewed drive for self-awareness and personal development gained through the leadership and personality classes. Similarly, participants SP-05M, SP-06F, and SP-07I reported gaining positive insights from P2KK. What was initially perceived as “restriction” and “coercion” in the program eventually transformed into a point of awareness and internal motivation, pushing them to become more responsible and disciplined individuals.

The participants’ experiences were classified into three key dimensions. First, in the **spiritual dimension**, they felt a stronger connection to Allah, increased motivation in performing religious practices, and engaged more deeply in self-reflection. Second, in the **social dimension**, they learned values such as tolerance, responsibility, and collaboration; particularly through group assignments and simulation activities. Lastly, in the **personal dimension**, participants reported increased self-confidence, better time management, and enhanced emotional regulation. The participants’ experiences can be summarized as presented in the following table:

Table 1. Dimensions of Experience and Associated Perceptions

Dimension of Experience	Perceived Impact
Spiritual	Feeling closer to Allah, developing enthusiasm for worship, and engaging in self-reflection
Social	Learning tolerance, responsibility, and teamwork through group assignments and simulations
Personal	Gaining self-confidence, developing time management skills, and improving self-control

Students’ reflections demonstrated a shift in mindset, enhanced academic motivation, and a more active and meaningful approach to campus life. P2KK was perceived as a space for nurturing Islamic identity, religious discipline, and leadership character as presented in the following table

Table 2. Reflections and Character Development Outcomes of P2KK Participants

Participant Code	Key Reflection	Character Strengthened
SP-01N	Shift in mindset, stronger motivation, deeper campus engagement	Islamic personal character (worship adherence and social awareness)
SP-02U	Religious transformation, greater confidence in religious practice	Religious character (increased commitment to Islamic obligations)
SP-03N	Reinstated prayer discipline through habitual worship	Religious character (consistency in worship and faith practice)
SP-04R	Self-discovery and motivation for self-improvement	Religious leadership character (moderate religious insight and social soft skills)
SP-05M	Gained insight and awareness of personal responsibility	Religious leadership character
SP-06F	Improved discipline and sense of accountability	Religious leadership character
SP-07I	Developed awareness and motivation to act responsibly	Religious leadership character

From Al-Ghazālī’s perspective, character is formed through the habitual practice of worship and spiritual discipline, which serve as the implementation of *riyāḍah al-naḥs* (spiritual training) and *tazkiyah al-naḥs* (soul purification). This process emphasizes the importance of repeated religious practices as a means to develop noble character that is stable and deeply rooted within the individual.

Meanwhile, according to Thomas Lickona, the P2KK program reflects the principles of character education through the stages of moral knowing, moral feeling, and moral action.

Nurul Hidayah et al, Character Development of University Students through the P2KK Program: A Phenomenological Study at the University of Muhammadiyah Malang

Students are not only taught Islamic values cognitively, but are also encouraged to internalize them emotionally through various activities, and to put them into action in their daily lives. This approach fosters comprehensive ethical awareness within each student.

Within David Kolb's experiential learning framework, character development in the P2KK program occurs through four interrelated stages of learning. Concrete experiences are embodied in field activities such as outbound training, leadership simulations, group discussions, and congregational worship. Reflection on these experiences takes place through daily contemplation sessions, which guide students in understanding the values embedded in each activity. Abstract conceptualization emerges as students formulate core values such as responsibility, empathy, and spirituality through classroom discussions and learning materials. The final stage, active experimentation, is reflected in the application of these values in students' post-program lives—such as involvement in campus organizations, participation in social activities, and the continued practice of religious worship. These four stages make P2KK a holistic, transformative, and sustainable learning process.

The P2KK program thus serves as a comprehensive medium that integrates all three aspects of character formation: spiritual habituation (Al-Ghazālī), moral internalization (Lickona), and reflective experiential learning (Kolb), leading to holistic character development.

These three approaches simultaneously address the following educational domains:

- 1) Affective domain – the cultivation of attitudes, values, and moral awareness (Al-Ghazālī and Lickona)
- 2) Cognitive domain – the understanding of values and reflective thinking (Lickona and Kolb)
- 3) Psychomotor domain – the real-world application of values through active learning (Kolb and Lickona)

Hence, the process of character building in P2KK is not limited to understanding or behavior alone, but also embeds values comprehensively into the students' souls, minds, and actions.

These findings resonate with Al-Ghazālī's concept that character is formed through habits and spiritual effort (mujāhadah) (Ghazali, 2014). Human character is not fixed at birth, but can be shaped through education, training, and repeated practice. It can also be transformed through intention, effort, and a supportive environment (Qasimi (Al), 1995). Al-Ghazālī outlined four stages in character formation: mujāhadah (sincere struggle), riyāḍah al-nafs (spiritual training), teacher role-modeling, and an enabling environment (Ghazali (Al), 2015).

The P2KK program provides a structured space for the habituation of values such as religiosity, sincerity, discipline, and responsibility, through a spiritual and collaborative approach. Activities that initially felt burdensome gradually became natural as they were internalized subconsciously.

Practices like night prayers (tahajud), congregational prayers, and tilawah (Qur'anic recitation) during P2KK serve as a form of riyāḍah al-nafs, embedding character through repeated spiritual acts. This aligns with the principle that the soul can be trained until noble character becomes stable and habitual (Ghazali (Al), 2008).

The experiential learning model adopted in P2KK mirrors Kolb's cycle (Kolb, 1984), reflected in the sequence of concrete experiences (e.g., dormitory life schedules), reflective observation (discussions and evaluations), abstract conceptualization (value reinforcement through lectures), and active experimentation (real-life application in campus life). The interactive approach and supportive classroom atmosphere help students overcome anxiety and adapt more easily. This proves that experiential learning (EL), when applied effectively, yields positive outcomes and helps students learn and adjust successfully. EL in this context engages students in discussions, demonstrations, games, role-playing, and problem-solving (Hidayah et al., 2024).

In contrast to studies like Almaidah, (2018), which focused on program structure, this study highlights the personal meanings internalized by students during the P2KK experience. While not all students exhibited immediate change, nearly all acknowledged a lasting impact in terms of character formation after the program.

Beyond its formal structure, P2KK acts as a real-life training ground for character education. Activities such as waking early for night prayers, engaging in group discussions, and delivering short religious speeches (kultum) create space for students to practice honesty, discipline, and empathy—core elements of Lickona's theory: moral knowing, moral feeling, and moral action (Lickona, 2018).

P2KK has succeeded in addressing the challenge of character formation in the disruption era by balancing the spiritual, social, and personal dimensions of student development. Character education, as evidenced here, is not instantaneous, it requires a consistent and nurturing ecosystem, as demonstrated in the P2KK program.

IV. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that the P2KK program at University of Muhammadiyah Malang represents an effective and comprehensive model for character education in the context of Islamic higher education. Key findings include:

1. P2KK is holistic and sustainable, grounded in the theoretical integration of Al-Ghazālī (spiritual discipline), Thomas Lickona (moral development), and David Kolb (experiential learning).
2. Character formation is fostered through three interconnected processes:
 - a) Spiritual habituation (e.g., repeated worship and discipline),
 - b) Moral internalization (values experienced emotionally and intellectually),

Nurul Hidayah et al, Character Development of University Students through the P2KK Program: A Phenomenological Study at the University of Muhammadiyah Malang

- c) Reflective and experiential learning (learning by doing and reflecting).
3. Student transformation occurred across three dimensions:
 - a) Spiritual: increased religiosity and worship awareness,
 - b) Social: enhanced empathy, responsibility, and leadership,
 - c) Personal: improved discipline, self-regulation, and ethical maturity.
4. Previously burdensome activities—such as strict daily schedules and intensive religious routines—eventually became internalized as positive habits supporting long-term character development.
5. The program successfully engages all three educational domains:
 - a) Affective (attitudes, values, moral sensitivity),
 - b) Cognitive (value understanding and reflection),
 - c) Psychomotor (application of values in real-world behavior).

This study highlights several practical recommendations for educators, institutions, and policymakers:

1. Ongoing support and refinement of P2KK and similar programs are essential to adapt to the evolving needs of students in the era of disruption and complexity.
2. The integrative character education model can serve as a reference framework for other universities, particularly those aiming to balance intellectual, moral, and spiritual outcomes.
3. Implementation quality depends on trained facilitators, who are well-versed in Islamic pedagogy, experiential learning methods, and adolescent psychology.
4. Policy alignment is necessary to institutionalize character education programs that emphasize ethical and spiritual growth alongside academic success.
5. Holistic ecosystems must be cultivated, ensuring that character development is not treated as a one-time intervention but as an embedded, continuous, and culturally rooted process.

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